

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Nsobundu****FIRST NAME: Chigozie****PROGRAM CODE: DSSD****COURSE CODE: ACA - 401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied XUS UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

QUIZ: A SUMMARY OF ASSESSMENT

1. **Essay writing requires two main important aspect of thinking.**

- Creative and critical thinking¹**
- Critical and Inference reasoning
- Creative and Analytical thinking
- Logical and Imaginative reasoning

2. **When writing research papers, what is the most important thing to avoid?**

- Paraphrasing
- Citation
- Quotation

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 3.

Plagiarism²

3. **What is the most common research question in academia?**

Conceptual Questions³

Applied Questions

Practical Questions

Hypothetical Questions

4. **What are the criteria for the usefulness of evaluating sources during literature review?**

Relevance and Reliability⁴

Validity and Relevance

Accurate and Reliability

Complete and Precise

5. **What is the general rule of thumb in writing conclusion?⁵**

Provide at least two conclusions for each finding.

Provide one conclusion for each finding.

Provide more than one conclusion for each finding.

Provide at least three conclusions for each finding.

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 5.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of research Papers, Thesis and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 16.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, 28.

⁵ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (California: SAGE Publications, 2008), 157.

6. **Transcribing qualitative data from audio to text, synthesizing data and making analytic decisions falls under which category in research writing.**
- Literature Review
 - Methodology and Research Approach
 - Analysing and Interpreting findings.
 - Analysing data and reporting findings.⁶**
7. **A semicolon is used to ----- rather than use a -----**
- Used to signal direct speech rather than use a comm.
 - Combine two sentences rather than use a comma.⁷**
 - Round brackets rather than use a comma.
 - Used to write numbers in words or figures rather than use a comma.
8. **Which of the abbreviation categories is usually written in capital letters and take no points?**
- Truncations
 - Acronyms
 - Contractions
 - Initialisms⁸**

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, 95.

⁷ Tim Cooper, et al., *English Style Guide. A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 7th ed. (European Commission, 2011), 16.

⁸ Cooper, et al., 28.

9. **The citation source that is used by placing a parenthetical citation including author, date, and relevant page numbers.**

- Citation Style
- Bibliography Style
- Author-Date Style⁹**
- Parenthetical Style

10. **In research writing, quotation that is less than four lines and enclosed in quotation marks is called?**

- Direct Quotation
- Note Quotation
- Run-in Quotation¹⁰**
- Block Quotation

⁹ Kate L. Turabian, 87.

¹⁰ Kate L. Turabian, 208.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.